

Use of video tutorials for Active Learning and PBL in Coastal Engineering subject

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Abstract

In the past, workshops lessons on the Coastal Engineering subject were held in computer classrooms, where different problems related to the subject were resolved. The professor guided the students through each of the sessions, while at the same time the students solved them on their computers, asking any questions that arose and, finally, completing the tasks individually, either in the classroom or at home. However, this methodology usually presented serious difficulties to students, particularly the impossibility in some cases to follow the synchronised rhythm of the explanations, which led to a reduction in attendance and a drop in academic performance. To improve it, a teaching model based on Active Learning and Project-Based Learning (PBL), supported by of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) resources, was proposed. Students now acquire the competencies by carrying out their vulnerability analysis projects. Audio-visual material (video tutorials) recorded by the professors solving a case of study in a guided way, covering the computer sessions were created and shared. Students therefore can view those videos asynchronously as many times as necessary, using the device that suits them best (TV, computer, tablet or mobile phone) at the same time as they carry out their work. The practical sessions are now dedicated to the development of a vulnerability analysis project. Assignments and supplemental materials from instructors keep learners engaged and accountable. The results obtained show an increase in attendance and follow-up of the computer sessions, as well as a reduction in the drop-out rate of the subject and an improvement in the quality of the project submitted by the students at the end of the course. In addition, an increase in academic performance and global students' satisfaction has been detected.

Keywords: Engineering Education; Video Tutorial; Computer Lesson; Project-Based Learning.

1 Introduction

The development of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) has led to updating the teaching methodologies traditionally used. Its implementation has implied a real educational innovation in the use of more active teaching-learning methodologies, supported by the special relevance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) as a systematic resource to help improve the training process of the students (Cañete et al., 2012). The number of hours of autonomous work required for students to assimilate the contents developed is explicitly stated in the methodological planning of each subject, contained in the corresponding teaching guide. As Aguila et al. (2013) indicate, in order to facilitate the autonomous work of students, there may be a multitude of curricular material available on the Internet (notes in digital format, exercise resolution, guided computer practice, video tutorials, etc.) that adapts to the learning pace of the students, without time restrictions, and that allows reinforcing and complementing the contents developed in the classroom lessons, promoting the acquisition of knowledge, skills and professional competences. Similar experiences have been succeeded developed in the field practices sessions with success (Pagán et al., 2021).

The Active Learning and Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology have been implemented in recent years in different European degrees and universities, especially in the field of engineering (Lehmann et al., 2008). Compared to traditional lectures, this new approach offers several advantages: on the one hand, students have a leading role in on-site sessions, increasing their motivation and satisfaction. On the other hand, active methodologies and ICTs are naturally incorporated into learning processes, and various transversal competencies can be developed and assessed in the classroom (Zabalza et al., 2016). In this methodology, learning is organised through a real problem or project proposals. The problem or project is the starting point of the learning process, and its resolution involves integrating contents and procedures in a learning activity,

facilitating a better understanding of the contents of the subject and working on their application to real situations (Lehmann et al., 2008). Its main characteristics are:

- It focuses on the development of projects whose characteristics are often defined by the students themselves, based on guidelines and main aims set by the tutor.
- The project is presented at the beginning of the process, becoming the guiding thread of the learning process, developing the students' competencies. Thus, the concepts, procedures and attitudes included in the learning objectives of the subject will be assimilated.
- Learning activities are carried out in teams, in a collaborative and active environment among students.
- There is continuous monitoring of student learning, both at the group and individual level, encouraging critical reflection, self-assessment and co-assessment, with the tutor acting as a guide and advisor in the process.
- It involves the development of specific skills and abilities, such as leadership, the capacity for coordination, consensus, decision-making, communication skills, and the sharing of roles and responsibilities.
- These abilities and new skills are acquired through active learning.

For this purpose, video tutorials are a key ICT resource that makes it easier for students to learn the contents (Colomo & Aguilar, 2017). Video tutorials can be reproduced as many times as the students require, stopped during playback to repeat a specific part, and viewed from anywhere on computers, TVs or mobile devices depending on the needs of the students, which makes the video format an essential resource for offering quality training (Brame, 2016). The duration of video tutorials is an element of discussion (González et al., 2010). While some experiences have been developed during a traditional practice session lasting between 1h - 1h 30min, capturing the screen using specific software and recording the audio with the teacher's explanations and the doubts or questions that arise for students during the practical session (González et al., 2010), most focus on the development of videos specifically to support lessons. Knowledge pills allow access to concrete information very quickly, but with the restriction that their content is very limited and, therefore, their learning activities are very targeted. The availability of a good collection of short videos as part of the didactic material of a subject, made available to students, allows them to execute and consume them autonomously as a training complement, thus improving the effectiveness of knowledge transfer (Alonso-González et al., 2021).

This research focuses on the development and implementation of strategies and methodologies in the implementation of formative assessment in practical subjects, assessing them based on objective quality criteria, such as academic results, and subjective criteria like the anonymous opinion collected from students and their own experience of the teaching staff throughout its implementation. Specifically, a new methodology is proposed for the development and evaluation of the computer sessions on the subject Coastal and Oceanic Engineering for the Degree in Marine Sciences at the University of Alicante. The incorporation of new tools in our teaching practice, many of them based on ICTs, will improve the independent learning of students. Thus, the specific objectives to be achieved by this teaching experience are the following: (i) to investigate the different resources available offered by ICTs for the guided resolution of computer-based practical sessions and project-based learning, (ii) to design materials for the guided resolution of the practical sessions adapted to the subject Coastal and Oceanic Engineering of the degree in Marine Sciences of the University of Alicante, (iii) to implement the use of the designed resources in the teaching of the current course and finally, (iv) to evaluate the results of the experience using the information adequately collected using questionnaires to students.

2 Method

2.1 Context and participants

This educational experience was implemented in the subject Coastal and Oceanic Engineering, which is part of the 4th year of the Degree in Marine Sciences, pursued during the first semester and with six European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits. It aims to provide students with the acquisition and application of the necessary knowledge involved in coastal phenomena, as well as in the design and

construction of facilities and engineering works in the maritime and coastal environment. The development of the subject is carried out through theoretical classes, practical problems, computer practice and field visits. In the academic year 2021-2022, there are a total of 18 students enrolled. The computer lessons are conducted over 5 sessions of one hour each, distributed throughout the course so that the concepts learnt during the theory sessions can be applied.

Throughout the sessions, the teacher made an example in class of obtaining the Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI) on a coastal strip, obtaining the geomorphological, oceanographic and marine community parameters. To do this, he used a geographic information system, QGIS, a new software for students, which can be complex without some previous knowledge. The students were, at the same time, doing their work on their computers, asking questions and, finally, completing the tasks autonomously, either in the classroom or, in most cases, at home, given the lack of time to complete them in the classroom due to the slow pace of the explanations. Moreover, students usually complained about the impossibility in some cases to follow the synchronised rhythm of the explanations, which led to a reduction in attendance and a drop in academic performance.

As a method of evaluation, at the end of the course the students must hand in a report describing the procedure followed and the results obtained from the calculation of the CVI. The mark obtained represented 10% of the total of the course.

2.2 Description of the experience

Firstly, a design phase was carried out in the initial weeks of the course and before the start of the computer-based practice sessions. All available information on Active Learning and PBL, supported by ICT resources, was compiled. After exploring the different methods and resources available (notes in digital format, existing videos on the Internet, creation of specific video tutorials, etc.), scenarios for testing new methodological tools and innovative techniques for improving the teaching-learning processes were developed and implemented. The aim is to achieve greater student engagement, which should have a positive impact on the results of the continuous assessment throughout the course.

The best way to implement the PBL and Active Learning methodology was discussed among all the participants in the network, and the conclusion was to carry out group workshops on obtaining CVI in different sectors of the coast. Professors met to establish the quantity and appropriate content of each of the video tutorials necessary to carry out this experience, in line with the development of the contents of the subject and with the programming of the computer-based practices foreseen in the schedule. Two video tutorials were created containing the guided development of the computer exercises, with the step-by-step resolution of a practical case of obtaining the CVI in a coastal stretch different to those assigned to the groups. For each video tutorial, files were prepared with the title, description, contents, format and duration, as well as screenshots of the cover and part of the video (Figure). In addition, to reflect the real workload, the weight of this part of the course has been increased to 30% of the total mark, with 60% for the report to be submitted with the methodology and results obtained and 40% for the presentation and oral defence of the project carried out.

For the evaluation of the experience, the instrument to be used will be mainly a questionnaire designed to find out the students' assessment of the new methodology implemented and the video tutorials, including possible answers where appropriate. Moreover, we will also compare the attendance and the results of the evaluation of the current academic year in which the experience will be implemented with the reports of previous years.

As described above, the new methodology based on PBL and Active Learning has been implemented in the academic year 2021/22. The students will carry out a project in groups of between 2 and 3 people whose objective is to obtain the Coastal Vulnerability Index of various stretches of coastline of similar length and complexity. Sessions 1, 3 and 5 will be done in classic workshop lessons, while for sessions 2 and 4 the viewing of the video tutorials is implemented.

This activity was planned to be carried out asynchronously, although it was recommended to be carried out before the date assigned to the respective sessions in order to be able to dedicate the session (1 hour each) to the resolution of doubts and/or problems that arose for each student. The video tutorials have been created with the OBS Studio software, and have been published on Youtube with access only to the students' e-mail

addresses. This platform was chosen for its versatility and accessibility from different devices (PC, Tablets, Smartphones, TVs...) as well as for providing higher quality viewing and for being widely known by all students, regardless of their digital skills.

TITLE: Shoreline evolution analysis using QGIS 3.20		TITLE: Obtaining the Coastal Vulnerability Index – CVI – with QGIS 3.20	
DESCRIPTION: Video tutorial with guided resolution of the process of obtaining and analysing the evolution of the shoreline from aerial images, as well as obtaining change statistics, using QGIS 3.20		DESCRIPTION: Video tutorial with a guided resolution of the process of obtaining and analysing a coastal vulnerability index, using QGIS 3.20	
CONTENTS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the software and working environment. • Downloading and opening of orthophotos. • Shore line and dune foot vectorization. • Base line vectorization. • Creation of shoreline and dune surfaces. • Creation of transects. • Obtaining evolution statistics. • Sedimentary budget. Erosion/Acretion zones 		CONTENTS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of CVI. • Geomorphological variables. • Hydrodynamic variables. • Vegetation variables. • Definition of vulnerability ranges. • Obtaining the CVI in QGIS 3.20. • Creation of maps with the results. 	
FORMAT:	.mp4 4K video	LENGTH:	48:38

Figure 1: Sheet describing the video tutorials

Finally, after the implementation of the experience, the degree of student satisfaction was evaluated using the evaluation instrument described in section 2.2 above. To ensure maximum participation, a 10 min slot was set aside at the end of the last practical session where all the students were present and were asked to fill in the questionnaire anonymously. Once the answers were collected, they were analysed to draw the results and conclusions shown below. In addition, an evaluation was made of the overall quality of the work presented in comparison with that of previous years, as well as an analysis of academic performance and attendance and monitoring of the practical sessions.

3 Results

It is important to highlight the high participation of the students in answering the questionnaire, achieving 100 % participation. This was influenced by the fact that a few minutes were spent in a class in which all 18 students were present and asked to fill in the questionnaire, emphasising its anonymous nature.

The results of the questions asked are shown below. Inquired about their opinion on the use of PBL & video tutorials (Figure 2a), 100 % of the students considered their use to be of interest, as well as that it has helped them in the learning process. As for the teaching methodology (Figure 2b), 89 % opt for the one followed in this course, viewing the videos asynchronously at home before the workshop session and dedicating that hour to progressing with the assigned work and resolving doubts. Only 2 student indicates that he/she prefers to receive a classic synchronous explanation and to have the videos as support, while not having the video tutorials is an option that nobody chooses.

Regarding the reasons why the students consider that the methodology implemented in this course (video tutorials for the guided resolution of computer exercises and PBL) has improved the learning process (Figure 2c), all indicate as advantages of having the video tutorials that when developing the project, they have been able to consult the explanations again, that they have been able to repeat the explanations as many times as they have needed and that in this way it has become easier to follow the course at their own pace. 78 % percent consider that this gives them more time to understand the exercises proposed, and only 61 % see the advantage of the video tutorials as being able to follow the explanations if they do not attend the workshop in person.

Figure 2: Responses on the use of video tutorials and PBL methodology

Regarding the perception of how the video tutorials influence the consolidation of the concepts and knowledge explained (Figure 3a), 63 % consider that they influence Very, while the remaining 38 % indicate that they influence them Extremely. In other words, all the students considered that the use of video tutorials had a positive or very positive influence on the teaching-learning process. When asked about the aspects that they consider most relevant to be present in the video tutorials and that help them to learn (Figure 3c), 100 % agree that the accuracy of the explanations is the most relevant, followed by 78 % who mark the graphic design as an aspect to be considered, and only two students indicate that the clarity language used is relevant. This implies that the students attach importance to receiving correct and precise explanations, and also to the graphic format of the video, whereas they dominate the technical terms used by not giving them so much importance.

About the advantages they have observed in the use of video tutorials in the learning process (Figure 3c), the students could choose multiple predefined answers, as well as add other advantages that they considered were not present, which none of them did. The only answer that everyone ticked, and which is therefore shown to be the greatest advantage of this methodology, is *Being able to repeat the explanation and the commands used as many times as one needs*. This is followed by *Following the pace of the class in a personalised way* (89 %), and this response corresponds to one of the findings of this research. Traditionally, teachers were faced with the problem of having to adapt the pace of their lessons to students who had more difficulties in following them synchronously or who had less digital skills, causing, on the one hand, that the time allocated to each lesson

was often scarce because they could not advance all the desired concepts and procedures, and on the other hand, that the students were frustrated, causing a reduction in attendance and a decrease in academic performance. At the same time, more advanced students or those with greater digital competencies saw their learning progress delayed, with abundant time-outs that also caused the same effect of disconnection, sometimes even generating some friction between classmates.

Figure 3: Responses on the advantages and influences of the proposed methodology on learning.

This negative effect has disappeared with the proposed methodology, as viewing the video tutorials allows each student to follow the pace of the explanations they need, even if they are viewed during the workshops, and the teacher can deal with any doubts that arise in a personalised way without slowing down the teaching pace. 78 % of students agree that this is an advantage, since being able to view the video tutorials at any time makes it easier to follow their own pace of learning at the time when they are most inclined. Comments not included in the survey but communicated to the teaching staff by the students indicated that they watched the videos on their smartphones/tablets on public transport on the way to class, during the dead time between subjects or even while doing their housework. This possibility of viewing the video tutorials on several devices is also pointed out as an advantage by 78 % of respondents, as it allows them to have the video tutorial on one screen to follow the explanations and on the other screen to carry out the procedure at the same time. Finally, the better visualisation of the content, an aspect that also used to be problematic in workshops sessions, due to the resolution of the projector, is only indicated as an advantage by 39 % of the students.

The length of the video tutorials was rated as adequate by 72 % of the students, while 28 % considered it excessive (Figure 4a). It should be recalled that the duration of the video tutorials was about 50 minutes, practically the same as the face-to-face session. However, for some students this duration is often considered excessive, as they are used to a faster audiovisual consumption, like knowledge pills (Colomo & Aguilar, 2017). As a proposal for improvement, for future courses we will consider dividing the video tutorials into blocks of a shorter duration (10-15 min). It will be the same content but presented in a more convenient way to find the parts of interest for the students. Even so, 89 % would like to repeat this experience in other subjects (Figure 4b), while 11 % indicate that they might like to do so, which indicates that the methodology we have implemented has been very well accepted.

Figure 4: Assessment of the experience.

This is confirmed in Figure 4c, where, when asked about the overall evaluation of the experience, i.e. the learning based on carrying out a project to calculate the coastal vulnerability index with video tutorials that solve the computer-based practice sessions in a guided manner, 61 % indicated that the experience was Very Good, and 39 % that it was Good, with no negative evaluations. The quality of the explanations is rated 50 % as Good or Very Good, while the graphic design of the tutorials is rated as Good (61 %) or Very Good (39 %). In other words, in all cases there is a positive assessment by the students. No negative comments or proposals for improvement have been received from them regarding the experience developed in this course.

Figure 5 show an increase in attendance (100 % in this academic year 2021-22), as well as an improvement in the quality of the project submitted by the students at the end of the course, even considering the quality requirements were higher than previous courses as the value of the final mark of the workshop on the overall subject score was augmented up to 30 %. In addition, an increase in academic performance has been detected, obtaining the best scores of the last 7 academic courses.

Figure 5: Evolution of the percentage of attendance and success at workshop and overall subject score. Students enrolled were 16, 17, 15, 19, 18, 16 and 18, respectively.

4 Conclusion

This research has investigated the different resources available offered by ICTs for the guided resolution of computer-based practical sessions and project-based learning. Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Active Learning methodology were implemented, creating two video tutorials for the guided resolution of the computer sessions adapted to the subject Coastal and Oceanic Engineering of the degree in Marine Sciences of the University of Alicante. The results obtained show an increase in attendance and engagement in the workshops, as well as an improvement in the quality of the project submitted by the students at the end of the course. Students pointed out that the greatest advantages of this methodology are, firstly, being able to repeat the explanation and the commands used as many times as one needs. Secondly, following the pace of the class in a personalised way. The PBL approach with video tutorials was also well evaluated as a help to assimilate the concepts, procedures and attitudes included in the learning objectives of the subject. In addition, an increase in academic performance and global students' satisfaction has been detected. Thus, this experience can be evaluated as a complete success, encouraging the teaching staff to maintain in the following academic years and even expanding to other subjects where computer practice is relevant.

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